

945358-BIGPICTURE
Central Repository for Digital Pathology
WP3 - Data collection & management

D3.04 - Report on employment of quality control automation

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Abstract

There are large variations in histopathology slide preparation and digitisation in digital pathology. Inevitably this also applies to the Bigpicture slide contributions. This is not necessarily a problem, as one of the advantages of AI is that it can be trained, with a large and diverse dataset, to overcome the variations. However, by improving the production of the images at every stage we ensure that all images meet a minimum level of quality before submission, and that the resultant image contains enough information to be "fit for purpose". In turn this makes the dataset more consistent and reduces the variability overhead for AI development. This report presents the first stages on quality control work in Bigpicture, starting with understanding the quality variations, reporting on them to raise awareness and the potential impact for the pre-clinical and clinical nodes respectively. The results indicate wide variability for colour management from the slide scanners. This could be mitigated by wide scale adoption of a colour profile, such as the ICC profile, if adopted by all scanner manufacturers and image handling and display software. Automated tools are being looked at for quality control of submitted slides and meta data but these are still in early stages of development. There is still much work to do on comprehensively improving quality in digital histopathology, but this early work does indicate that understanding the problem is half the solution and our understanding on the variability of quality in digital pathology is increasing daily and will contribute to better data, better AI and ultimately better outcomes for patients.

Introduction

At the outset of this project, quality was recognised as a fundamental component of the Bigpicture ethos. Digital pathology, and indeed pathology itself, has variable quality management at each stage of the digital image production. Each stage can have a potential variation, and these can compound on each other. Does this matter? Arguably with a large enough dataset these variations can be mitigated in the AI implementation. However conversely improving quality at the earliest, and every stage, of the image production reduces the burden of variability on AI, and in theory makes the development of algorithms easier and more consistent if used with a quality data set itself. At this stage we believe effective AI is a blend of improving image production, increasing the data set size/variability and improvements in AI development. But we do not actually know the variability across all the slide contributing partners, and therefore the first stage in this process has to be increasing that knowledge of the landscape of variability and working through these to quantify them, make recommendations on minimising them and ultimately setting standards. This has been

the primary aim of the Quality Coordination Centre Taskforce set up across all the work packages in the Bigpicture to coordinate and support the implementation of qualitative stage. This report therefore highlights some of the work that has been done to date to do this, the very real practical implications of these for the pre-clinical and clinical notes and also to update on activities to automatically apply quality control both to the image data sets and the meta data. The adage “quality in equals quality out” is at the core of Bigpicture and this report highlights our early steps towards this that we believe will ultimately accelerate development and adoption of AI in digital pathology in a sustainable and scalable way, ultimately contributing to faster AI adoption.

Background

This document pertains to deliverable D3.04, focusing on employment of quality control automation. Initially this was conceived as a specific piece of work that looked at automatically validating inputs to the repository i.e. for image or meta data errors. However much of this is predicated by knowing ‘what is good’ and much of this work has been undertaken by the Quality Control Coordination Taskforce into understanding the landscape of quality in digital pathology. Therefore, the QCC Taskforce is the primary party executing this report, alongside valuable contributions from external work package members across clinical and non-clinical cohorts.

This report focuses on assessing and improving the quality control processes within the Bigpicture consortium, particularly in the realm of digital pathology. It aims to understand and address variations in image quality across different contributing partners, ultimately enhancing the consistency and reliability of the dataset.

Chapters one to two of the report align with its purpose by delving into various aspects of quality control:

Chapter 1 – Reports from the QCC Taskforce and the implications for the pre-clinical and clinical nodes:

- a. Presents findings from the Sierra pilot study evaluating colour profile variability across different whole slide imagers (WSI) used by slide contributing partners. This is important as it allows us to understand the landscape of inherent scanner variability across the slide contributing partners and work towards recommendations and

strategies to minimise this variation. This also allows us to consider standardising colour profiles in the future..

- b. Provides instructions and guidelines for slide contributing partners to ensure consistent quality in slide submissions. It outlines minimum standards and considerations for pre-scan and post-scan quality checks.
- c. Offers practical updates from pre-clinical nodes on addressing challenges identified in the quality control assessment, demonstrating collaborative efforts to improve quality standards.
- d. Reports practical updates from clinical nodes, highlighting their actions and responses to the quality control reports, and emphasizing the importance of implementing quality measures in their workflows.

Chapter 2: Quality Control Automation for meta data and image quality

- a. Details efforts for automating image quality assessment, aiming to flag slides with poor quality for further review.

Conclusion – summary comments from Taskforce leads (DSB and EBT)

Provides summary comments from the QCC Taskforce leads, reflecting on the early-stage work conducted to improve image quality. It emphasises the importance of implementing solutions, such as colour profiling and automated quality checks, while considering the needs of both pre-clinical and clinical nodes.

Overall, these chapters collectively contribute to the overarching goal of enhancing the quality and consistency of digital pathology within the Bigpicture repository, ultimately supporting more robust AI development and improving patient outcomes.

Results

Chapter 1 part a:

Pilot study for the Sierra slide for assessing variability in color profile for the range of whole slide imagers in the slide contributing partners. Dated: Wednesday, August 30, 2023

This work was designed to get initial data from a limited cohort about Whole Slide Imaging (WSI) colour using the Sierra colour slide (see below), as well as collect feedback on the process used to collect this data, this was to prepare for a larger future Sierra survey due to be initiated in Q1 2024. The Sierra slide is formatted to the same specifications as standard glass tissue slides for WSI imager. The slide incorporates 55 patches of a material that mimics the way stains bind to tissue, which when stained using common histology and cytology stains from across the colour gamut of pathology creates an accurate measure of ground truth colour as found in histological and cytological samples. (figure 1.1)

The aim of this survey was to compare the WSI images of a Sierra slide across a range of WSI scanners, the WSI images analysed are termed 'direct scanner output' data as the centers were asked to scan the slide as they would a tissue slide and images were collected immediately after the image was produced by the scanner, i.e. no additional post production colour calibration was applied, although colour calibration may still be occurring within the scanner software itself during file creation).

Our aim was to use this data to measure the variation in colour introduced by the WSI (whole slide image) scanners across the Bigpicture network. The data below describes the colour of this image compared to the reference colour of the slide as well as the variation of this data across the cohort. Please note we did not calculate the ICC colour profiles but simply looked at the output colour variation from the input reference values. The method for data collection was to circulate one Sierra slide around early adopter sites and collate the data. Multiple clinical institutions were included which covered a range of scanners and experiences. A scanning 'Standard Operating Procedure' (SOP) was sent to all participants along with advice to ensure consistent scanning. The resultant scan data were uploaded to SharePoint and analysed using the FFEi Sierra Validate and Standardise (V&S) Analyser software which gave colour variation (dE) results. These results were returned to the individual sites and an anonymised summary report generated. (additional detail can be found in Chapter 1 part d.) In total there were 37 submissions from 7 Bigpicture beneficiaries.

Figure 1.1. Overview of the Sierra WSI colour assessment slide (FFeI)

Make	Model
3D Histech	Pannoramic P1000
3D Histech	Pannoramic Flash P250
Hamamatsu	S60
Hamamatsu	XR
Hamamatsu	S360
Leica	Aperio AT2
Objective Imaging	Glissando
Olympus	VS200
Precipoint	M8

Table1: Makes and models represented across the Pilot cohort.

For each patch on the Sierra slide we know the measured ‘reference colour’ of each patch of the Sierra slide, as well as the colour that was presented in the digital image after scanning, the ‘direct scanner output’ data. The data presented in this report represents the numeric value of the colour difference between this ‘reference colour’ and the ‘direct scanner output’, measured in Delta E, a CIE (international commission on illumination) defined measure of change in visual perception of two given colours. For guidance, the values can typically be interpreted as values of 1-2 Delta E as perceptible only through close observation, 3 – 10 perceptible at a glance, and at 100 colours are exact opposite (interpretation can change depending on exact use case).

In Figure 1.2 each submitted image from every unique WSI machine is represented along the X-Axis, each image in this figure is obtained from a different physical WSI machine but may be the same make and model and may be within the same institution. The coloured data points represent on the

Y axis the numeric value of the colour difference between the ‘reference colour’ and the ‘direct scanner output’ (measured in Delta E) for each individual patch on the Sierra slide. The colour of the dot represents the reference colour of the patch. Numbers on the X-axis represent the different WSI scanner make/models.

Figure 1.3 represents the same data as Figure 1.2 but with median (IQR) deltaE from all patches across the Sierra slide. Data for each unique scanner (red) is shown alongside the average data from all scanners of the same make and model within the cohort (blue).

Figure 1.2: Delta E between ‘reference colour’ and the ‘direct scanner output’ from each unique WSI machine across the pilot cohort. Each image in this figure is obtained from a different physical WSI machine but may be the same make and model and may be within the same institution. Grey dashed lines at 3 and 10 delta E.

Figure 1.3: Delta E between ‘reference colour’ and the ‘direct scanner output’ from each independent WSI machine across the pilot cohort (red) compared to cohort average for that scanner (blue). Each image in this figure is obtained from a different physical WSI machine but may be the same make and model and may be within the same institution. Grey dashed lines at 3 and 10 delta E.

In Figure 1.4 we show data in which optional replicate scans were performed on the same WSI scanner (this was not mandated or carried out routinely, so not all WSI scanners from the cohort are represented). Data above the same letter on the X-Axis represent the same physical WSI machine. In many cases settings were changed slightly between replicate scans, for example magnification or the number of focus points, and the time period of the replicate data collection was not mandated so is also a variable. Details of these changes between replicates are not described herein, these variables will likely be addressed in more detail in a future Sierra survey. Each submitted WSI image is represented along the X-axis as individual bars. The letters on the X-axis represent the different individual WSI scanners. The coloured data points represent on the Y axis the numeric value of the colour difference between the ‘reference colour’ and the ‘direct scanner output’ (measured in Delta E) for each individual patch on the Sierra slide. The colour of the dot represents the reference colour of the patch. The table below graph describes summary DeltaE statistics for each image presented in the graph.

Figure 1.4: Delta E between ‘reference colour’ and the ‘direct scanner output’ from replicate scans on some of the WSI machines across the pilot cohort. Data above the same letter represent the same physical WSI machine. In many cases settings were changed slightly between replicate scans, for example magnification or the number of focus points, and the time period of the replicate data collection was not mandated so is also a variable. Grey dashed lines at 3 and 10 delta E.

Conclusion:

The data presented in this work shows the range of colour profiles across the slide contributors and scanners. Understanding this variation holds significance for Bigpicture, as it enables AI developers to refine their algorithms or devise strategies to mitigate such variations, potentially through scanner ‘typing’ or characterisation. If an ICC colour profile was generated from this data (optionally from FFEi) this could be used to standardise scanner outputs by re-mapping any output data or including in meta data for consideration at review/analysis. This is not applied at this stage as not all systems are able to apply the profile, but a recommendation of this work is that the ICC profile should be applied across all manufacturers of scanners and slide display software. Such standardisation would not only reduce variation, but also enhance the consistency across the image repository within Bigpicture.

The next phase of this study involves a scaling up to include preclinical sites. The impact of this work and the scale up are discussion in part 2 a and b for the pre-clinical and clinical work respectively.

It is worth noting that all data submitted to the study was anonymised for simplicity and to avoid any potential confidentiality or GDPR issues.

Chapter 1 part b:

Instructions for slide contributing partners to provide consistent quality of slide contributions.

Dated: June 20, 2022

The goal of the Bigpicture consortium is to develop digital pathology image datasets that can be used to develop robust AI classifiers. On that basis, the content submitted should represent “real world” quality and be derived from a variety of laboratories to represent the variation in processes seen in the real world.

Bigpicture are therefore not looking to restrict contributions to the database and we accept the need for a broad range of images, image quality and presentations. This document is for guidance, and outlines best practice. We appreciate that documenting or achieving some of these standards may present practical challenges to slide contributors, so currently there are no mandated quality checks prior to submission.

However, there is an expectation that the images supplied and uploaded will meet a minimum level of quality with respect to its utility (see below).

Minimum expected standards:

There is an expectation that the scanned data will be representative of what would be acceptable for its intended clinical or pre-clinical diagnostic use. If it is not, it should not be submitted.

As a basic principle:

- any reported pathological finding or diagnosis associated with the digital slide image should be clearly discernible on the slide by a pathologist qualified to make that observation.
- the quality of the submitted digital slide image should not negatively affect the reproduction of the reported finding or diagnosis by a second pathologist (or AI tool).

Our expectation is that there will be iterations to this guidance over time that will aim to improve the quality of the repository. It is also recommended that any prospective scanning follows a quality protocol. A generic protocol is suggested in Appendix 1.

Direction of travel:

In future guidelines, it is likely the completeness of parts of the associated meta data may be quality

checked prior to upload (see part 3a). It is also likely the recording of any minor image defects and artefacts will be encouraged. This will be supported by a defined 'Image artefact ontology'. A first draft of the artefacts under consideration for the ontology can be found in Appendix 2.

Chapter 1 Part b Appendix 1: Proposed generic quality protocol

Pre-Scan:

Quality checks for the following features:

- Slide features that could affect scanner performance:
 - o Absence of breaks, chips, scratches (of the slide or coverslip)
 - o Excessive mounting medium, spill out of cover slip onto edges.
 - o Insufficient mounting medium, excessive bubbles.
 - o All slides have a single coverslip, coverslip covers all the tissue/coverslip does not hang over the side of the slide.
 - o Excessive Ink marks, writing, stain residue
 - o Slides are fully cured (not "wet")
 - o Slides are very clean and in good condition- no dirt, no fingerprints
- Appearance of the tissue(s) is sufficient for end use: not incomplete; damaged; torn, streaks...etc.*
- Appearance of the label (pre-anonymization): Correct, complete and readable, does not cover any tissue, does not extend beyond slide label area, does not extend beyond edge of slide
- Scanner is up to date with in-house or manufacture advised maintenance schedule.
- Scanner settings are correct for end use.
- Trained, competent staff utilising the scanner and handling slides.

Post-Scan:

Quality checks for the following features that could trigger a re-scan:

- Scan completed without error and image file created: File is of the appropriate file format and of expected size.
- Appearance of the digital slide: Image complete and representative of the original slide. • Presence within the digital slide of artefacts that would prevent end use: abnormal colour; blurry area; insufficient resolution... etc.
- Images comply with any relevant data anonymisation processes.

- Presence and completeness of required meta data: Including required annotations and compliance with any relevant anonymization processes.

The standards quality checks need to reach should be evaluated and designated in house to ensure the highest quality for the intended end use.

Summary:

This document sets out the minimum standards of quality or slide submission to the Bigpicture repository. There may be differences between the pre-clinical and clinical requirements and these are reflected in part 2 a and b.

NB.

- Please note that version 2 of this report is currently being developed.

Also note that any method of quality assessment is relative to the local institution, it is accepted that this may cause some variation but we are not trying to remove variation, but to ensure these issues have been considered and that the resultant images are suitable for the purpose they were intended.

Chapter 1 part c:

Update from pre-clinical nodes on the reports from part 1.

Based on the reported findings from the pilot Sierra and discussion with the non-clinical node, unique challenges for the non-clinical slide contributors were identified:

- Purpose of the study
- Mandatory or optional
- Confidentiality
- Issues around not using the ICC profile.
- Issue around CRO
- Issues around workflow
- Scanner calibrated

A workshop was held in Dec 2023 between the QC taskforce and non-clinical leads to address these challenges, the aggregate responses from the non-clinical node are summarised below.

- Purpose of the study
 - This study is to understand the landscape of variability to a) inform the variability of

the data set, and b) highlight the need for consistency.

- Mandatory or optional
 - Participation is optional for those in the non-clinical node
- Confidentiality
 - While each participant will get an individualised copy of their won results, the data will be consolidated and anonymised in a summary report which will be generated at the end of this study
- Issues around not using the ICC profile.
 - As identified the ICC profile should be used or made available to inform the impact of scanner variation on image fidelity. This is not something we can propose at this time as some scanners/viewing software may not be able to use these profiles. So currently the data is for information only.
- Issue around CRO
 - Any centre submitting slides are eligible for using the Sierra slide. We appreciate this may be difficult with CROs but the recommendation is to co-ordinate between slide contributors the different CROs used and ensure only one response from each.
- Issues around workflow.
 - The use of Sierra does add an extra stage into the workflow but is only one slide per WSI. The expected impact should be minimal.
- Scanner calibrated.
 - Ideally any scanner should be calibrated for normal operational use. If it is not this will be reflected in the Sierra results. Therefore, the use of the Sierra slide and Sierra submissions should be 'as used' operationally.

These responses were satisfactory to the participants and the non-clinical Sierra study will commence in 2024, with the option by non-clinical participants to opt-out of the study.

2) Considerations from the non-clinical slide contributors on the use of the slide submission guidelines

During the workshop, the following concerns were raised by the non-clinical leads should they choose to use the slide submission guidelines.

- Impact for service
 - As not all studies are performed in-house, a concern was raised that following the slide submission guidelines would impact on the service in general. Like the use of Sierra, the slide submission guidelines are recommendations and are not being enforced at this time
- Suitability of guidelines

Given that clinical and non-clinical slide submitters can have different workflows, it was questioned as to whether or not the guidelines, if followed, were also suitable to the non-clinical workflow. Currently the understanding is that the guidelines take into account both clinical and non-clinical workflows

- Mandatory or optional
 - The question arose as to whether use of the guidelines was mandatory, or to be used as a guide. It was reiterated that the slide submission guidelines are recommendations at this time

Chapter 1 part d:

Practical update from the clinical node on the implications of the QCC reports

Action from clinical nodes related to Chapter 1 (participation in Sierra slide pilot study):

Seven Bigpicture beneficiaries from different clinical sites participated as described in part 1a in this report. Communication was facilitated through the clinical node coordination network, but executed through direct contact between an appointed person at each laboratory/biobank and a project Co-ordinator from NPIC/Leads Teaching Hospital NHS Trust.

The purpose of the study was clear and all sites volunteered to participate. There was clear instruction on how to scan the slide and submit the data. Shipment of a delicate good (alike a glass slide as Sierra slide is), was a minor logistic challenge and added some more time effort than expected from both parties. As it was only the Sierra slide that was scanned at one occasion, no major issues on confidentiality nor workflow was raised from the participants. The individual results from the pilot survey have been reported back to every sites so the participants have had the ability to review routines and procedures of calibration and scanning, manual actions that indirectly will increase quality awareness and output for future digital images. However, the conclusion and knowledge on need of ICC profiles in scanning systems is an awareness that will not help us directly in the project

but will be transferred into future standardization protocols and requirements.

To summarize participation in the Sierra slide pilot study was successfully completed from 7 beneficiaries with the results as described in 1a, leading to good experience on the potential impact of scanner colour variation for future work on QCC values and measurements within the field of digital pathology.

Action from clinical nodes related to part 1b (instructions for slide contributing partners to provide consistent quality of slide contributions):

Beneficiaries within WP3 that will have the role of slide contributors have a variety in background experiences of digital pathology and scanning. Eight of the twelve data contributing WP3 beneficiaries from various clinical environments have significant experience of scanning slides of large volumes (>1000 slides/day) for clinic or research before the project began and have already implemented digital pathology in their clinical routines, as represented in table 2. They have well developed experience from local validation of scanning systems as well as validation/training programs to support the individual pathologist in the transformation from diagnostic work on slides in light microscopy to the scanned WSI in the digital environment. Also, the pathology departments are involved in different external quality assurance programs related to laboratories performance on different stains or diagnostic reproducibility. These laboratories have levels of quality that, with the support of defined methodologies and external QC in daily work, relates to the most important post-scan quality tool; the pathologist. The pathologist confidence to conclude a diagnosis on digital image is the gold standard for the intended use in digital pathology. Nevertheless, different local thresholds of laboratory quality output, including the variations in scan results leads to good practical experience to define minimum standards as presented in 1b.

For participants that have little or no experience of scanning or use of digital pathology and intend to start their scanning process as part of Bigpicture action, e.g. biobanks, good support is available in the description of quality checks and will be evaluated and designated in house to ensure the highest quality for the intended use.

To summarize the actions from clinical nodes have been involvement and participation in QCC TF activities (meetings and webinars) and surveys. Conclusions of the surveys are presented as results of the proposed quality checks as outlined in pre-scan and post-scan checks in *chapter 1 part b* of this report.

Data Contributing Beneficiaries (anonymised)	WP3 and data contributing Beneficiaries with major experience of scanning slides of large volumes (e.g. >1000 slides/day) for clinic or research before the project started	WP3 and data contributing Beneficiaries with minor experience of scanning slides of large volumes (e.g. <1000 slides/day) for clinic or research before the project started
A	1	
B	1	
C	1	
D	1	
E		1
F	1	
G	1	
H	1	
I		1
J		1
K	1	
L		1
Total number	8	4
Proportion	67%	33%

Table 2: This table details the involvement of WP3 and other data-contributing beneficiaries, categorising them based on their level of prior experience in scanning slides of significant volumes (e.g., >1000 slides/day) for clinical or research purposes before the project's inception. The table features the diverse spectrum of background experience in digital pathology and scanning, with a notable majority of beneficiaries possessing substantial prior expertise.

Chapter 2:

Update of image quality automation

To ensure that the BigPicture repository contains high-quality data, a full manual inspection of every uploaded slide would be the gold standard. However, this would also be infeasible as it would entail domain experts going over 3 million digitized slides in great detail. Instead, we have opted for a (semi-automated) approach that involves developing an algorithm to automate the most cumbersome QC task: identifying and assessing the extent of common image artifacts. Deliverable 4.7 further reports this work in detail but is summarised in its abstract:

“Data quality is one of the leading metrics determining the value of any public repository. Although manual data curation is the gold standard for ensuring quality, manual curation quickly becomes untenable when repository sizes approach thousands of images, let alone millions, as in the case of the Bigpicture repository. Additionally, the images included in the Bigpicture repository are not regular images but whole-slide images

that are gigapixels in size and whose quality cannot be judged briefly but require careful inspection at high resolution, increasing the burden of manual curation.

This deliverable aims to investigate and develop an automated method for basic image quality control. Specifically, the most common cause of poor image quality in digitized histopathology is staining or scanning artifacts. We investigated existing approaches to (semi-)automatically identify artifacts in whole-slide images identifying best practices. Subsequently, we developed a Bigpicture artifact detection model using those best practices to identify use cases. A training set for model development containing artifact classes such as pen markers, out-of-focus regions, dust, and air bubbles, among others, was collected. The model was optimized using an internal validation set and subsequently validated on a diverse set of 500 whole-slide images from more than ten laboratories and across different tissues and stains. The model was evaluated using manual annotations on the pixel and slide levels. Performance was deemed adequate for integration in the Bigpicture infrastructure (average Dice coefficient is 0.83, with a slide-level accuracy of >90%, which will be further refined during the project's runtime).

In addition to the artifact detection model, we also investigated the possibility of generating realistic artifacts to validate QC algorithms, the results of which were subsequently scientifically published.

The code, data, and a web-accessible version of the model will all be published through the consortium GitHub and the Bigpicture platform to allow reuse and refinement. This allows slide contributors to run the model on their local infrastructure before submitting data to Bigpicture. In addition, we are currently planning to add the model to the data submission infrastructure as soon as the inference hardware is in place and operational.”

There are two important sidenotes to this endeavour: 1) it is not our goal to make sure all data in the repository is completely artifact-free, as this would reduce the usefulness of the repository by not mirroring real-world data. The goal is to automatically flag slides that have such poor quality that they are effectively unusable. 2) We are not claiming that slides would be acceptable for a specific diagnostic or research question. For example, a single out-of-focus tile on top of a cluster of metastatic cells might be an unacceptable artifact for some use cases. In contrast, in other use cases, it would be fine if 20% of the slide is affected by artifacts.

At the start of the development of the BigPicture artifact detection algorithm, we first surveyed the current state-of-the-art, which was and is relatively limited, especially with respect to automated

approaches.

The most well-known and highest-cited QC algorithm for digitized histopathology is the HistoQC software package [Janowczyk et al. *JCO Clin Cancer Inform* (2019), Chen et al. *J Pathol* (2022)], which includes tools and a GUI for several types of artifacts, for example, air bubbles, out-of-focus regions, and pen markings. Although an excellent example of open-source software tested across different centres and tissue types, it lacks several common tissue artifacts, such as tissue folds, ink, and dust, to name a few. Additionally, it is still a highly involved manual process in which users must run separately and visualize different modules. Others have built on this initial effort, offering more automated tools. For example, Berman et al. [PLOSOne, (2023)] developed the SliDL package, a digital pathology machine learning library with a larger scope than just QC but including artifact segmentation. However, the package is not maintained, was only validated on 61 slides, and only offers a single ‘artifact’ class. Last, Haghighat et al. [Sci Rep, (2022)] offer another, similar solution in PathProfiler, which also includes an algorithm for artifact detection. Sadly, this algorithm was only trained and validated for a single use case, specifically assessing prostate biopsies. Last, none of these algorithms have been validated for toxicological pathology or immunohistochemically stained slides.

Conclusion

Integration of QC across the consortium. Summary comments from the QCC Taskforce leads.

This report outlines some of the early stage work conducted in the Bigpicture consortium to try and improve image quality across the whole of the Bigpicture repository. The results presented show the wide variation of whole slide imager variation of colour, which may affect the development of algorithms in the future. Knowing this allows us to form a strategy of influence to ensure that manufacturers use a colour profile on their whole slide imaging scanners which can also apply through the digital image journey including the display software and monitors. However, before the slides are even scanned, we need to ensure that even the most basic of quality measures are taken to ensure the data set is as good as it can be, this includes basics such as cleaning the slides recognising faults and checking the data to ensure it is uploaded correctly. This applies not only to images, but also to the meta data where an incorrectly reported image will not be retrieved at a later date for use in AI training. Of course, while it is essential to identify problems, suggest solutions, and make recommendations based on them, we must prioritise the end user in this project, namely the pre-clinical and clinical nodes. Therefore, respective leads from these areas have reviewed the impact of the quality report and commented on them. Important key themes from these are that the ICC colour profile should be implemented, or the impact will be minimised. Training and experience also appear important for quality slide submission and the impact of all these ‘additional’ tasks needs to be considered with respect to CROs and busy clinical labs respectively. Automated methods of analysing submitted slides and meta data are being developed but these are early stage and the full benefit of them is not being realised at this time however the direction of travel is that they should be achievable solutions that are also part of the QCC strategy.

In summary we have presented the early-stage work understanding the landscape of quality variation amongst slides contributing partners for the Bigpicture project, and the interventions to implement. Ultimately “quality in does equal quality out” and improving the quality of the data set for in the Bigpicture repository, whilst also continuing to ensure the data set diversity, should support robust algorithm development. But this is just the start of the journey and there is still much to do to before we no longer have to consider quality as a separate “issue”, and it is embedded in the culture of digital pathology from the patient to the AI.